

Sensitivity of multifrequency brain MR elastography to acute caffeine intake

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Abstract

Background: Brain magnetic resonance elastography (MRE) is an emerging quantitative neuroimaging technique that noninvasively maps brain tissue viscoelasticity. For both clinical applications and research settings, it remains crucial to determine the extent to which MRE-derived viscoelastic parameters are influenced by extrinsic modulators.

Purpose: To evaluate whether caffeine induces measurable changes in brain tissue mechanics using MRE.

Study Type: Prospective study.

Study Population: Sixteen healthy adult volunteers (10 men, 6 women; mean age 26.1 ± 2.4 years).

Field Strength/Sequence: 3 T system (Siemens MAGNETOM Cima.X) with a brain multifrequency MRE methodology with echo-planar imaging (EPI) readout.

Assessment: Each participant underwent one MRE acquisition before and after the oral intake of 200 mg caffeine. Shear wave speed (SWS) and penetration rate (PR) were quantified in whole brain, white

matter, subcortical gray matter, and cortical gray matter regions using atlas-based region-of-interest (ROI) analysis in MNI152 space.

Statistical Tests: Symmetric relative difference (SRD), paired t-Tests, Pearson correlation, and Bland-Altman plots were processed to determine caffeine induced changes in brain tissue mechanics.

Results: Caffeine ingestion induced tissue-specific marginal reductions in SWS, but statistically significant in whole brain ($p = 0.04$) and cortical gray matter ($p < 0.001$), and statistically insignificant in white matter ($p = 0.56$) and subcortical gray matter regions ($p = 0.64$). Mean SRD were -1.05% , -0.27% , -1.62% , and -0.89% in whole brain, white matter, cortical gray matter, and subcortical gray matter, respectively. PR showed no significant changes. Despite the small effect of caffeine intake on SWS, reductions in cortical gray matter significantly correlated with increases in systolic blood pressure ($p = 0.03$).

Conclusion: Caffeine induces minimal changes in human brain viscoelasticity at the whole-brain and cortical gray matter levels. The statistically significant differences observed in these areas do not translate into major percentage changes, and the measured mechanical properties remain consistent with the reproducibility reported in another prior study.

Keywords: magnetic resonance elastography · brain · caffeine · shear wave speed · penetration rate · quantitative neuroimaging

Introduction

Magnetic resonance elastography (MRE) is a quantitative magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) technique for noninvasive assessment of tissue viscoelasticity analyzing externally induced mechanical waves through phase-contrast imaging. MRE has been increasingly applied in the fields of neurological diseases such as Alzheimer's disease [1-4], multiple sclerosis [5], Parkinson's disease [6, 7] and neuro-oncological research [8-10]. Although MRE is highly sensitive to intrinsic mechanical contrasts, the measured properties are also affected by acquisition parameters [11-14], vibration frequency [15-18], and reconstruction approaches [19-22]. Further, data on the technique's sensitivity to acute physiological or pharmacological modulations are still limited. Such information is crucial for clinical translation, as transient changes in cerebral perfusion, vascular pulsation, and intracranial pressure can affect MRE-derived tissue mechanical properties independent of chronic tissue alterations or pathology [23-25]. The present study addresses this gap with an investigation of the acute effects of caffeine, the probably most widely consumed psychoactive substance worldwide [26], on brain viscoelastic properties using multifrequency MRE.

Sixteen healthy volunteers underwent identical multifrequency MRE acquisitions before and 30 to 50 minutes after ingestion of 200 mg caffeine with standardized acquisition and reconstruction. Shear wave speed (SWS) and penetration rate (PR) were quantified in whole brain, white matter, cortical gray matter, and subcortical gray matter regions with atlas-based region-of-interest (ROI) analysis in MNI152 space. The study thereby establishes proof-of-concept for MRE-based quantification of acute physiological state effects and provides quantitative data for the detection of subtle modulations in brain viscoelasticity influenced by pharmacodynamic confounders.

Material and Methods

The experimental setup, including image acquisition, data correction and MRE inversion, image registration and spatial normalization, as well as region-of-interest (ROI) analysis, was performed in a manner largely consistent with our previously performed brain multifrequency MRE reproducibility study [27].

Study design and participants

Sixteen healthy adults participated in this prospective single-center within-subject caffeine intervention study (10 men, 6 women; mean age 26.1 ± 2.4 years; range 19 to 33 years). The study protocol received approval from the institutional ethics committee of the Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg (application 23-389-Bm). All participants provided written informed consent prior to study participation. Inclusion criteria comprised age ≥ 18 years, absence of neurological or cardiovascular disease, no regular medication, and no contraindications to MRI. Exclusion criteria comprised prior major head injury or neurosurgical intervention, clinically relevant alcohol abuse, pregnancy, and the presence of any MRI-incompatible implanted device. In addition, participants were required to be moderate caffeine consumers (maximum regular daily intake ≤ 400 mg.day⁻¹ according to the European Food Safety Authority guideline [28]). Known caffeine hypersensitivity or adverse reactions, cardiovascular disease, and use of medications known to interact with caffeine metabolism led to exclusion from the study. All examinations were performed on a single day using identical multifrequency MRE acquisition and reconstruction protocols. Each participant underwent baseline vital checks (*Step 1*) and MRE imaging (*Step 2*), followed by oral administration of a tablet that contained 200 mg caffeine (*Step 3*), and a second vital check and MRE scan 30 to 50 minutes after ingestion (*Steps 4, 5, and 6*), as illustrated in *Figure 1*. During the vital checks, quantitative blood pressure (systolic and diastolic) was measured at the participant's wrist twice, and sleepiness was assessed qualitatively using the Stanford Sleepiness Scale (SSS) [29]. In addition, participants pulse was recorded during the measurement of each MRE sequence and averaged over the duration of the sequence afterwards. During the interval between the two scans, participants were supervised.

Figure 1: Study design.

Experimental setup

The caffeine intervention study employed a single 3 T MRI scanner (Siemens MAGNETOM Cima.X) with a 64-channel head coil. The scanner was located at the *Zentrum für medizinische Physik und Technik*, Erlangen, Germany. Figure 2 illustrates the experimental setup. An active pneumatic driver (VibroR42, THEA Devices GmbH, Germany) generated the mechanical vibrations. Compressed air supplied the driver, and plastic hoses conveyed it to two pillow-like passive transducers. The transducers worked in phase opposition and rested over the occipital scalp at approximately the 5 and 7 o'clock positions relative to the head. A strictly standardized protocol guaranteed consistent head positioning and transducer placement for both the pre-caffeine and post-caffeine acquisitions of each participant.

Figure 2: Experimental setup.

Image acquisition

A multifrequency MRE sequence that incorporated motion-encoding gradients (MEG) with first moment nulling and echo-planar readout was used to acquire three-dimensional brain tissue displacement data [30]. Vibration frequencies of 20, 25, 30, and 35 Hz were applied, as in [21]. Corresponding pneumatic pressure levels of 175, 225, 250, and 350 mbar controlled the vibration amplitude. External vibrations and the motion-encoding gradients of the MRE sequence were locked through synchronization of the wave generator digital clock with the MRI scanner clock. The MRE sequence timing was adapted relative to the external wave phase and sampled eight evenly spaced time points over one vibration cycle for each frequency [30]. Motion encoding occurred along the three orthogonal spatial directions (x , y , and z). In total, 96 MRE head volumes were measured, resulting from the four vibration frequencies, eight time points, and three MEG directions. MRE acquisition parameters comprised a repetition time (TR) of 6540 ms, echo time (TE) of 70 ms, an acquisition matrix of 116×116 , 60 slices, an isotropic voxel size of $2.0 \times 2.0 \times 2.0 \text{ mm}^3$, and a phase-encoding (PE) direction along the anteroposterior axis. Each imaging session contained echo planar imaging (EPI) volume pairs acquired with reversed phase-encoding directions (anteroposterior and posteroanterior) to enable correction of geometry distortions caused by susceptibility differences and long echo-planar readouts [31]. All other imaging parameters stayed identical to those of the MRE sequence. For distortion correction, a total of six EPI volumes were acquired, corresponding to two phase-encoding directions and three motion encoding gradient directions. Anatomical reference images consisted of T1-weighted structural scans acquired with a magnetization-prepared rapid gradient echo (MPRAGE) sequence. The T1-weighted sequence parameters included a TR of 2200 ms, TE of 2.46 ms, an acquisition matrix of 256×256 , 208 slices, and an isotropic voxel size of $0.8 \times 0.8 \times 0.8 \text{ mm}^3$.

Data correction and MRE inversion

MRE magnitude and phase data passed through a multi-step correction and inversion pipeline to generate quantitative maps of shear wave speed (SWS) and penetration rate (PR). The complete workflow ran in MATLAB (version R2024b, Natick, Massachusetts, US) and is illustrated in *Figure 3*. First, a Laplacian-based phase-unwrapping algorithm removed phase wraps from the raw phase images

(*Step 1*). This method was originally described by Dittmann et al. and is provided in the appendix of reference [30]. Second, a two-dimensional in-plane motion correction procedure implemented in the statistical parametric mapping toolbox (SPM, version 25.01.02, University College London, UK) compensated for subject motion (*Step 2*) [32]. Here, the first head volume was used as a reference for the remaining 95 volumes. Third, TOPUP from the FMRIB software library (FSL, version 6.0.7.17, Oxford University, UK) corrected geometric distortions (*Step 3*) [32]. Fourth, the brain extraction module (BET) in FSL produced a brain mask that restricted all further analysis to intracranial tissue (*Step 4*). Fifth, temporal fast Fourier transformation (tFFT) extracted the wave motion at the applied driver frequencies from the time-resolved phase data (*Step 5*). Sixth, an interslice phase correction step compensated for phase offsets between slices (*Step 6*). Finally, mechanical property reconstruction was performed using the wavenumber-based multifrequency dual-elasto-visco method (*k*-MDEV), which is publicly available online at <https://bioqic.charite.de> (*Step 7*) [22, 33]. This inversion procedure estimated the complex-valued wavenumber $k^* = k' + ik''$ from a plane-wave decomposition of the measured wave field at a single vibration frequency. The real and imaginary parts of the wavenumber followed [21]:

$$k'_{d,c,f} = \|\nabla \arg(u_{d,c,f})\|, \quad (1)$$

and

$$k''_{d,c,f} = \left\| \frac{\nabla |u_{d,c,f}|}{|u_{d,c,f}|} \right\|, \quad (2)$$

where the indices d , c , and f denote the plane wave propagation direction, the displacement vector component, and the vibration frequency, respectively. Frequency-resolved SWS $_f$ and PR $_f$ were obtained through [21]:

$$\text{SWS}_f = \frac{\omega \sum_d \sum_c w}{\sum_d \sum_c k'_{d,c,f} w}, \text{ with } w = |u_{d,c,f}|^2, \quad (3)$$

and

$$\text{PR}_f = \frac{\omega \sum_d \sum_c w}{2\pi \sum_d \sum_c k''_{d,c,f} w}, \text{ with } w = |u_{d,c,f}|^2, \quad (4)$$

Final SWS and PR maps resulted from the average of the frequency-resolved volumes. All maps initially existed in EPI native space before subsequent registration.

Figure 3: Data processing.

Abbreviations: SWS, shear wave speed; PR, penetration rate; PA, posteroanterior; AP, anteroposterior.

Image registration and spatial normalization

Image registration and spatial normalization of the mechanical property maps occurred in MNI152 standard space. A multi-step MATLAB pipeline that employed FSL tools performed all transformation procedures and is illustrated in Figure 4. First (*Registration 1*), a linear within-subject registration aligned the skull-stripped (denoted by *) pre-caffeine (A) MPRAGE image to the corresponding post-caffeine (B) MPRAGE image with six degrees of freedom ($T1w.B^* \rightarrow T1w.A^*$). The resulting pre-aligned (denoted by ') post-caffeine image ($T1w.B'$) served as the reference for all subsequent processing steps of the post-caffeine session. For each pre- and post-caffeine intake condition, the skull-stripped magnitude EPI image underwent linear registration (*Registration 2A/B*) to the corresponding skull-stripped MPRAGE image with six degrees of freedom ($EPI_{mag}.A^*/B^* \rightarrow T1w.A^*/B'^*$). Next (*Registration 3A/B, Step 1*), each skull-stripped MPRAGE image ($T1w.A^*$ and $T1w.B'^*$) received linear registration to the MNI152 T1-weighted 2 mm brain template with 12 degrees of freedom ($T1w.A^*/B'^* \rightarrow MNI152^*$). A non-linear warp (*Registration 3A/B, Step 2*) from the non-skull-stripped MPRAGE image to the MNI152 template was then estimated with FSL FNIRT ($T1w.A/B \rightarrow MNI152$). The affine transformation matrix from the preceding linear step (*Registration 3A/B, Step 1*) served as the initial transformation. Finally (*Combining A/B*), the linear transformations and the non-linear warp

fields were concatenated into a composite transformation (SWS.A/B \rightarrow MNI152; PR.A/B \rightarrow MNI152). Application of this composite transformation to the SWS and PR maps of both conditions used spline interpolation. The procedure yielded mechanical property maps normalized to MNI152 standard space with an isotropic voxel size of 2 mm. All normalized images underwent visual quality control with particular attention to residual misregistration. The workflow depicted in *Figure 4* is to be understood such that the images or transformations specified along each arrow are propagated to and used as inputs for the subsequent processing step.

Figure 4: Registration process.

Region-of-interest analysis

Region-of-interest (ROI) analysis took place in MNI152 standard space and followed a compartment-based approach similar to that described by Hiscox et al. (2020) [34]. Tissue compartment masks originated from atlas-based probability maps. The analysis included a whole brain ROI based on the MNI152 brain mask, a white-matter ROI derived from the MNI white-matter map (threshold ≥ 0.75), a subcortical gray-matter ROI derived from the Harvard-Oxford subcortical atlas (threshold ≥ 0.75), and a cortical gray-matter ROI derived from the Harvard-Oxford cortical atlas (threshold ≥ 0.55). Mean SWS and PR values were extracted from each ROI for every subject and for both the pre-caffeine and post-caffeine conditions. Representative slices of the resulting ROI masks appear in *Figure 5*.

Figure 5: Color-coded visualization of the four brain regions analyzed: whole brain, white matter, subcortical gray matter, and cortical gray matter.

Statistical analysis

All statistical tests and analysis were conducted in MATLAB (version R2026a) with Statistics and Machine Learning Toolbox (version 25.2). The primary metric for quantifying caffeine-induced changes in viscoelastic brain properties was the symmetric relative difference (SRD), given by:

$$\text{SRD} = \frac{B-A}{(A+B)/2} \times 100, \quad (5)$$

where A represents baseline measurements and B represents post-intervention measurements. SRD values were spatially averaged in the individual brain regions shown in *Figure 5*. Prior to parametric statistical analysis, data normality was assessed for each tissue region and viscoelastic using the Lilliefors test with a significance threshold of $\alpha = 0.05$. All datasets satisfied the normality assumption.

Paired t -tests were then applied to test the null hypothesis that the mean difference equals zero (*i.e.*, no significant caffeine-induced changes). A significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$ was used to determine statistical significance. Effect size was quantified using Cohen's d coefficient, defined as the mean of the paired difference \bar{X}_{diff} divided by their standard deviation SD_{diff} [35]:

$$d = \frac{\bar{X}_{\text{diff}}}{SD_{\text{diff}}}. \quad (6)$$

Cohen's d coefficient was interpreted according to conventional effect size thresholds, where absolute values of approximately 0.2, 0.5, and 0.8 are interpreted as small, medium, and large effects, respectively [35]. Blood pressure (systolic and diastolic), pulse and qualitative sleepiness were recorded at baseline and post-intervention. Sleepiness was determined using the Stanford Sleepiness Scale, a validated 7-point self-report instrument quantifying current alertness or sleepiness on a numerical scale [29]. Changes in physiological markers were quantified as:

$$\Delta BP_{\text{sys}/\text{dia}} = BP_{\text{sys}/\text{dia},\text{B}} - BP_{\text{sys}/\text{dia},\text{A}}, \quad (7)$$

$$\Delta HR = HR_{\text{B}} - HR_{\text{A}}, \text{ and} \quad (8)$$

$$\Delta SSS = SSS_{\text{B}} - SSS_{\text{A}}, \quad (9)$$

where $BP_{\text{sys}/\text{dia}}$ denotes systolic and diastolic blood pressure, HR denotes heart rate, and SSS denotes the quantified sleepiness. The suffixes A and B indicate baseline and post-caffeine intervention measurements, respectively. To examine relationships between caffeine-induced tissue mechanical changes and systemic physiological responses, Pearson correlation was employed between all variables. Results were interpreted according to conventions of Cicchetti [36], where absolute correlation coefficients $r < 0.40$ indicate poor, $0.40 - 0.59$ fair, $0.60 - 0.74$ good, and $0.75 - 1.00$ excellent associations. Correlations were considered statistically significant at a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$.

Results

Analysis of mechanical property changes in the brain

Across mechanical parameters and brain regions, mean SWS values and corresponding standard deviation for pre-caffeine measurements were 1.07 ± 0.03 , 1.23 ± 0.03 , 1.30 ± 0.11 , and $1.00 \pm 0.02 \text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ and post caffeine-ingestion 1.06 ± 0.03 , 1.23 ± 0.04 , 1.29 ± 0.14 , and

$0.99 \pm 0.03 \text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ for whole brain, white matter, subcortical gray matter and cortical gray matter, respectively. The mean SRD served as the primary metric to quantify caffeine-induced changes. For SWS, significant negative mean SRD occurred in whole brain ($-1.05 \pm 1.82 \%$, $p = 0.04$) and cortical gray matter ($-1.62 \pm 1.12 \%$, $p < 0.001$), which indicated a marginal reduction in tissue stiffness after caffeine ingestion. White matter and subcortical gray matter also showed minor, but non-significant changes with $-0.27 \pm 1.76 \%$ and -0.89 ± 5.60 , respectively. PR exhibited no statistically significant mean SRD in any of the examined brain regions. A summary of SRD, total difference, Cohen's d and p value for SWS and PR across all ROIs is presented in *Table 1a* and *Table 1b*.

ROI	Shear Wave Speed				d	p
	SRD [%]		Δ [m/s]			
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
WB	-1.05	1.82	-0.01	0.02	-0.57	0.04
WM	-0.27	1.76	0.00	0.02	-0.15	0.56
SGM	-0.89	5.60	-0.01	0.07	-0.13	0.64
CGM	-1.62	1.12	-0.02	0.01	-1.33	<0.001

Table 1a: Effects of caffeine intake on SWS. Results are shown as SRDs and absolute differences (Δ), with SDs, Cohen's d , and p -values from paired t -tests.

ROI	Penetration Rate				d	p
	SRD [%]		Δ [m/s]			
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
WB	-0.11	5.39	0.00	0.03	-0.01	0.97
WM	1.16	6.26	0.01	0.05	0.20	0.46
SGM	0.31	11.49	0.00	0.07	0.06	0.83
CGM	-0.62	5.37	0.00	0.03	-0.11	0.66

Table 2b: Effects of caffeine intake on PR. Results are shown as SRDs and absolute differences (Δ), with SDs, Cohen's d , and p -values from paired t -tests.

Abbreviations: SWS, shear wave speed; PR, penetration rate; WB, whole brain; WM, white matter; SGM, subcortical gray matter; CGM, cortical gray matter; SRD, symmetric relative difference; SD, standard deviation; ROI, region of interest.

Group-averaged voxel-wise SRD maps in *Figure 6* provide a spatial visualization of SWS variations across the brain, between pre- and post-caffeine ingestion, for different slices. Across all slices, negative

SRD values were more prevalent than positive values, which indicates an overall reduction in SWS. The magnitude of these negative SRD values appeared higher in cortical gray matter, whereas in total white matter exhibited smaller negative changes and also contained more extended regions in all slices, with even strongly positive SRD values in slice 25.

Figure 6: Voxel-wise averaged SWS (left and middle) and SRD maps (right) across all subjects for different slices.

Abbreviations: SWS, shear wave speed; SRD, symmetric relative difference.

Violin plots in Figure 7 illustrate the distribution of SWS and PR values across the four brain regions for the baseline and post caffeine-intake measurement. For SWS, the distributions in cortical gray matter and whole brain exhibit a slight tendency toward lower values after caffeine intake, although the overlap between baseline and post-caffeine measurements remains substantial. Likewise, the distributions in white matter and subcortical gray matter ROIs differ only marginally between the two conditions. The observed shifts are small and should be interpreted in the context of the measurement reproducibility. In a previous work, relative differences of MRE measurements between two distinct scanners using the

same setup and reconstruction approach was determined from 1.38 to 1.52 % in whole brain, white matter and cortical gray matter [27]. PR distributions appear highly similar before and after caffeine administration across all brain regions, with no evident systematic change in their overall position or shape. The violin plots further highlight a higher inter-subject variability in subcortical gray matter compared to other regions, both at baseline and after caffeine administration.

Figure 7: Violin plots of region-averaged SWS and PR values of baseline scan (left violin-half) and post-caffeine scan (right violin-half) across four brain regions.

Abbreviations: SWS, shear wave speed; PR, penetration rate; WB, whole brain; WM, white matter; SGM, subcortical gray matter; CGM cortical gray matter.

Bland-Altman analysis

Bland-Altman plots evaluated the agreement between baseline and post-caffeine measurements for both SWS and PR across all ROIs (Figure 8). For SWS, the mean differences remained close to zero in white matter and subcortical gray matter regions and showed no consistent systematic bias. Notably, whole brain and cortical gray matter regions showed small systematic bias of -0.011 m.s^{-1} and -0.016 m.s^{-1} , with all datapoints appearing in the negative diagram half for cortical gray matter. The plots revealed narrow limits of agreement in whole brain, white matter, and mostly cortical gray matter. Subcortical gray matter exhibited wider limits of agreement compared with the other compartments. For SWS, most data points lay within the 95 % limits of agreement, with only few outliers directly at the border. For

PR, the mean differences were very close to zero across all ROIs ($< 0.005 \text{ m.s}^{-1}$), which indicates negligible systematic bias. However, the limits of agreement were broader than those observed for SWS, particularly in subcortical gray matter. The scatter of differences, but also of mean values appeared larger for PR than for SWS in all tissue compartments.

Figure 8: Bland-Altman plots of the SWS and PR obtained in baseline scan vs. post caffeine scan across four brain regions. Top row shows SWS and bottom row shows PR. Mean differences are visualized as continuous thick lines, whereas the limits of agreement are shown as dotted lines.

Abbreviations: WB, whole brain; WM, white matter; SGM, subcortical gray matter; CGM, cortical gray matter; SWS, shear wave speed; PR, penetration rate.

Associations between mechanical property changes and physiological markers

To investigate whether the observed changes in brain mechanical properties, albeit small, relate to physiological effects of caffeine, correlations between the relative changes in SWS and PR and systemic physiological parameters such as blood pressure (systolic and diastolic), pulse and feeling of drowsiness were examined. A significant negative correlation with fair association emerged in cortical gray matter between the relative change in SWS and the increase in systolic blood pressure after caffeine intake ($r = -0.53, p = 0.03$). Diastolic blood pressure showed no significant association with SWS changes in any ROI. Changes in pulse and sleepiness did not correlate significantly with alterations in SWS in any

tissue compartment. PR exhibited no meaningful correlations with any of the recorded markers (systolic blood pressure, diastolic blood pressure, pulse, or quantified feeling of sleepiness).

Discussion

This study demonstrates minimal alterations of brain mechanical properties induced by caffeine intake, measured by multifrequency MRE. The primary findings were small but statistically significant reductions in SWS in whole brain ($-1.05 \pm 1.82 \%$, $p = 0.04$) and cortical gray matter ($-1.62 \pm 1.12 \%$, $p < 0.001$) regions, while no significant changes were observed in white matter ($p = 0.56$) or subcortical gray matter ($p = 0.64$). In addition, PR remained unchanged across all investigated regions. These findings indicate, that the effects of acute caffeine intake on brain mechanics are limited and predominantly reflected in changes in SWS rather than PR.

The measured decrease in SWS primarily in cortical gray matter indicates that caffeine intake was associated with a small reduction in tissue stiffness. The mechanisms underlying this effect cannot be clearly determined from the present data. Caffeine acts primarily as an adenosine receptor antagonist [37]. It binds to adenosine receptors without activating them and thereby attenuates the effect of endogenous adenosine. As adenosine normally promotes neuronal inhibition and vasodilation, its blockade can result in increased neuronal activity and reduced vasodilation. At the cerebral level, this may result in changes in cerebral blood flow, blood volume and increased blood pressure [38, 39]. The significant correlation between cortical gray matter SWS reduction and increase in systolic blood pressure ($p = 0.03$) suggests that vascular factors may contribute, at least in part, to the measured mechanical changes. The predominance of effects in cortical gray matter tissue may be related to its dense vascular network [40, 41] and metabolic demand compared to white matter with its more structured fiber architecture and lower vascular density [40, 41]. However, the directionality and underlying physiological pathways remain incompletely understood. Nevertheless, the observed effects were small, with absolute values below 1.70 %, and close to the measurement variability of an earlier performed reproducibility study conducted on two distinct 3 T scanner using with the same measurement and processing setup [27]. Therefore, caution is warranted in their physiological interpretation.

The absence of systematic change of PR suggests that acute vascular or fluid-related changes do not substantially alter the damping properties captured by PR at the investigated frequencies. The observed caffeine-related changes in SWS, although small in magnitude, indicate that recent caffeine intake may introduce measurable variability in stiffness estimates, particularly in cortical gray matter. This suggests that controlling caffeine consumption may be important in comparison studies where small stiffness variations are expected. In routine MRE measurements, however, the relatively small absolute changes observed in this study (smaller than 1.70 %) indicate that acute caffeine intake (200 mg) is unlikely to represent a major source of variability in intrinsic mechanical contrasts.

Limitations

Several limitations must be considered when interpreting the results of this study. First, the sample size is moderate and limited to a cohort of young, healthy adults. This restricts the generalizability of the findings to other populations, particularly older individuals or patients with neurological or cardiovascular conditions. Age-related differences in brain viscoelasticity and vascular reactivity may influence the magnitude and direction of caffeine-induced effects.

Second, inter-individual variability in caffeine metabolism and habitual consumption may have influenced the observed responses. Although participants were restricted to moderate caffeine intake, differences in tolerance, receptor sensitivity, and baseline physiological state could not be fully controlled. These factors may contribute to the observed heterogeneity in SWS changes and reduce statistical power for detecting subtle effects in certain regions.

Third, the study design captures only a single post-intervention time point between 30 and 50 minutes after caffeine ingestion. While this window corresponds to the expected peak plasma concentration of caffeine [42, 43], it does not provide information on the temporal dynamics of the mechanical response. Earlier or later time points may reveal different magnitudes or patterns of viscoelastic changes.

Fourth, the magnitude of the detected SWS changes is small and approaches the lower limit of measurement sensitivity. Although the multi-site reproducibility of the employed MRE protocol has been demonstrated in [27], the observed effects remain close to the inherent variability of the method.

This limits the robustness of detecting subtle physiological modulation, particularly in regions where no significant changes were found.

Fifth, the absence of significant effects in white matter and subcortical gray matter must be interpreted with caution. These negative findings may reflect true physiological insensitivity, but they may also result from limited statistical power or from regional averaging effects in atlas-based ROI analysis

Sixth, the study relies on indirect physiological markers, such as blood pressure measurements, to interpret underlying mechanisms. Direct measurements of cerebral perfusion, blood volume, or metabolic activity were not acquired. As a result, the proposed vascular explanations for the observed mechanical changes remain inferential.

Finally, the study design did not include placebo-controlled condition. Without control intervention, it is not possible to fully exclude time-dependent effects, or nonspecific physiological fluctuations as contributing factors to the observed changes.

Conclusion

Small but statistically significant tissue-specific reductions in SWS were observed in whole brain and cortical gray matter, whereas white matter and subcortical gray matter showed small but statistically insignificant reductions. PR did not show significant changes across brain regions. The effects in cortical gray matter point to a region-dependent mechanical response, which potentially is related to differences in vascular density and neurovascular coupling. The significant association between increased systolic blood pressure and decreased cortical gray matter SWS further supports a potential contribution of vascular and hemodynamic factors to the measured changes. Despite reaching statistical significance, the magnitudes of the observed effects were small, with absolute SWS reductions smaller than 1.70 %. In the context of a previously performed reproducibility study, these findings suggest that acute moderate caffeine intake does not induce substantial alterations in brain mechanical properties.

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References

1. Murphy, M.C., et al., *Decreased brain stiffness in Alzheimer's disease determined by magnetic resonance elastography*. J Magn Reson Imaging, 2011. **34**(3): p. 494-8.
2. Murphy, M.C., et al., *Regional brain stiffness changes across the Alzheimer's disease spectrum*. Neuroimage Clin, 2016. **10**: p. 283-90.
3. Gerischer, L.M., et al., *Combining viscoelasticity, diffusivity and volume of the hippocampus for the diagnosis of Alzheimer's disease based on magnetic resonance imaging*. Neuroimage Clin, 2018. **18**: p. 485-493.
4. Hiscox, L.V., et al., *Mechanical property alterations across the cerebral cortex due to Alzheimer's disease*. Brain Commun, 2020. **2**(1): p. fcz049.
5. Fehlner, A., et al., *Higher-resolution MR elastography reveals early mechanical signatures of neuroinflammation in patients with clinically isolated syndrome*. J Magn Reson Imaging, 2016. **44**(1): p. 51-8.
6. Lipp, A., et al., *Cerebral magnetic resonance elastography in supranuclear palsy and idiopathic Parkinson's disease*. Neuroimage Clin, 2013. **3**: p. 381-7.
7. Lipp, A., et al., *Progressive supranuclear palsy and idiopathic Parkinson's disease are associated with local reduction of in vivo brain viscoelasticity*. Eur Radiol, 2018. **28**(8): p. 3347-3354.
8. Takamura, T., et al., *Relationship between Shear Stiffness Measured by MR Elastography and Perfusion Metrics Measured by Perfusion CT of Meningiomas*. AJNR Am J Neuroradiol, 2021. **42**(7): p. 1216-1222.
9. Friismose, A.I., et al., *Evaluating Measurement Stability in Glioblastomas Using Magnetic Resonance Elastography: Repeatability and Interobserver Agreement*. J Magn Reson Imaging, 2025.
10. Aunan-Diop, J.S., et al., *Repeatability of Magnetic Resonance Elastography-Derived Mechanical Parameters in Intracranial Meningiomas*. Journal of Magnetic Resonance Imaging, 2025. **62**(4).
11. Ozkaya, E., et al., *Precision and Test-Retest Repeatability of Stiffness Measurement with MR Elastography: A Multicenter Phantom Study*. Radiology, 2024. **311**(2): p. e233136.
12. Hiscox, L.V., et al., *Magnetic resonance elastography (MRE) of the human brain: technique, findings and clinical applications*. Phys Med Biol, 2016. **61**(24): p. R401-R437.
13. Guenther, C. and S. Kozerke, *Encoding and readout strategies in magnetic resonance elastography*. NMR Biomed, 2018. **31**(10): p. e3919.
14. Guenther, C., et al., *Analysis and improvement of motion encoding in magnetic resonance elastography*. NMR Biomed, 2018. **31**(5): p. e3908.
15. Sack, I., et al., *Non-invasive measurement of brain viscoelasticity using magnetic resonance elastography*. NMR Biomed, 2008. **21**(3): p. 265-71.
16. Sack, I., et al., *Structure-sensitive elastography: on the viscoelastic powerlaw behavior of human tissue in health and disease*. Soft Matter, 2013. **9**(24): p. 5672-5680.
17. Testu, J., et al., *Viscoelastic power law parameters of in vivo human brain estimated by MR elastography*. J Mech Behav Biomed Mater, 2017. **74**: p. 333-341.
18. Huang, X., et al., *Magnetic resonance elastography of the brain: A study of feasibility and reproducibility using an ergonomic pillow-like passive driver*. Magn Reson Imaging, 2019. **59**: p. 68-76.

19. Tan, L., et al., *Gradient-Based Optimization for Poroelastic and Viscoelastic MR Elastography*. IEEE Trans Med Imaging, 2017. **36**(1): p. 236-250.
20. Honarvar, M., et al., *A Comparison of Finite Element-Based Inversion Algorithms, Local Frequency Estimation, and Direct Inversion Approach Used in MRE*. IEEE Trans Med Imaging, 2017. **36**(8): p. 1686-1698.
21. Herthum, H., et al., *Cerebral tomoelastography based on multifrequency MR elastography in two and three dimensions*. Front Bioeng Biotechnol, 2022. **10**: p. 1056131.
22. Meyer, T., et al., *Comparison of inversion methods in MR elastography: An open-access pipeline for processing multifrequency shear-wave data and demonstration in a phantom, human kidneys, and brain*. Magn Reson Med, 2022. **88**(4): p. 1840-1850.
23. Arani, A., et al., *Acute pressure changes in the brain are correlated with MR elastography stiffness measurements: initial feasibility in an in vivo large animal model*. Magnetic Resonance in Medicine, 2018. **79**(2): p. 1043-1051.
24. Tzschätzsch, H., et al., *time-harmonic ultrasound elastography of the human brain detects acute cerebral stiffness changes induced by intracranial pressure variations*. Scientific Reports, 2018. **8**.
25. Schrank, F., et al., *Cardiac-gated steady-state multifrequency magnetic resonance elastography of the brain: Effect of cerebral arterial pulsation on brain viscoelasticity*. Journal of Cerebral Blood Flow and Metabolism, 2020. **40**(5): p. 991-1001.
26. Fredholm, B.B.B., K.; Holmén, J.; Nehlig, A.; Zvartau, E. E., *Actions of Caffeine in the Brain with Special Reference to Factors That Contribute to Its Widespread Use*. Pharmacological Reviews, 1999. **51**(1): p. 83-133.
27. Murk, S.L., F. B.; Rampp, S.; Vossiek, M.; Schattenfroh, J.; Guo, J.; Sack, I.; Doerfler, A.; Flé, G., *Inter-scanner reproducibility of brain multifrequency MR elastography*. 2026. **Preprint**.
28. EFSA Panel on Dietetic Products, N.a.A.N., *Scientific Opinion on the safety of caffeine*. EFSA Journal, 2015. **13**(5).
29. Hoddes, E., V. Zarcone, and W. Dement, *Development and Use of Stanford Sleepiness Scale (Sss)*. Psychophysiology, 1972. **9**(1): p. 150-&.
30. Dittmann, F., et al., *In vivo wideband multifrequency MR elastography of the human brain and liver*. Magn Reson Med, 2016. **76**(4): p. 1116-26.
31. Fehlner, A., et al., *Increasing the spatial resolution and sensitivity of magnetic resonance elastography by correcting for subject motion and susceptibility-induced image distortions*. J Magn Reson Imaging, 2017. **46**(1): p. 134-141.
32. Tierney, T.M., et al., *SPM25: open source neuroimaging analysis software*. Journal of Open Source Software, 2025. **10**: p. 8103.
33. Tzschätzsch, H., et al., *Tomoelastography by multifrequency wave number recovery from time-harmonic propagating shear waves*. Med Image Anal, 2016. **30**: p. 1-10.
34. Hiscox, L.V., et al., *Standard-space atlas of the viscoelastic properties of the human brain*. Hum Brain Mapp, 2020. **41**(18): p. 5282-5300.
35. Cohen, J.K., T. R., *Statistical Power Analysis for the Behavioral-Sciences, 2nd Edition*. Educational and Psychological Measurement, 1990. **50**(1).
36. Cicchetti, D.V., *Guidelines, Criteria, and Rules of Thumb for Evaluating Normed and Standardized Assessment Instruments in Psychology*. Psychological Assessment, 1994. **6**: p. 284-290.
37. Roehrs, T. and T. Roth, *Caffeine: sleep and daytime sleepiness*. Sleep Med Rev, 2008. **12**(2): p. 153-62.
38. Pelligrino, D.A., H.L. Xu, and F. Vetri, *Caffeine and the Control of Cerebral Hemodynamics*. Journal of Alzheimers Disease, 2010. **20**: p. S51-S62.
39. Boison, D., J.F. Chen, and B.B. Fredholm, *Adenosine signaling and function in glial cells*. Cell Death and Differentiation, 2010. **17**(7): p. 1071-1082.
40. Gawryluk, J.R., E.L. Mazerolle, and R.C.N. D'Arcy, *Does functional MRI detect activation in white matter? A review of emerging evidence, issues, and future directions*. Frontiers in Neuroscience, 2014. **8**.
41. Wilhelm, I., et al., *Heterogeneity of the blood-brain barrier*. Tissue Barriers, 2016. **4**(1).
42. Bonati, M., et al., *Caffeine disposition after oral doses*. Clin Pharmacol Ther, 1982. **32**(1): p. 98-106.

43. Mandel, H.G., *Update on caffeine consumption, disposition and action*. Food Chem Toxicol, 2002. **40**(9): p. 1231-4.